

POTENTIAL AND LIMITATIONS OF MODERN KRAFT BOILERS DESIGN IMPACT ON UTILITY SYSTEM OF A PAPER MILL – A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Modern high-performance regeneration boilers are equipped with certain features, only partly implemented in older boilers, boosting their steam output and cogenerated power from steam turbines. They include stepwise combustion air and feedwater preheating by low, middle and high pressure steam as well as flue gas coolers and HD concentrators. All these design features increase internal boiler steam consumption and some of them generate or provide middle and low potential heat that has to be utilized to justify them. As the boiler is incorporated into existing utility system with all its advantages and flaws, its performance is to some extent a reflection of the utility system state.

In our study we provide a wider view on the boiler performance, encompassing the boiler feedwater preheating train, condensates collection system and steam turbines into balance borders. Based on design and process data of a particular application in Slovakia we examine stepwise the individual boiler performance enhancement components and review their true performance and their impact on the utility system. Some of the resulting proposals seemingly sacrifice the boiler performance itself but bring benefit if the whole picture is considered. This may contradict the usual industrial praxis to strive for maximal performance of individual components with paying less heed to overall system performance.

Introduction

Regeneration boilers (also known as Tomlinson recovery boilers) appeared firstly in late 1930's as a result of the efforts undertaken to overcome the inefficient designs of the existing furnaces and smelt pots used in recovery of cooking chemical in paper mills¹. Initial boiler capacities were slightly above 100 tons of dry solids per day and even 30 years later it still reached only moderate 500 t_{DS}/day with produced steam parameters around 4 MPa and 400 °C². The state of the art of black liquor evaporators enabled to fire black liquor with max. 65 % dry solids content. A jump in produced steam parameters to 8 MPa and 480 °C has been enabled with boilers design evolution in the late 1980's accompanied with an increase in fired dry solids content to 75 % wt. and boiler capacities to 1750 t_{DS}/day. This in turn led to substantial SO_x emissions decrease as a result of chemicals regeneration improvement during black liquor combustion at higher temperatures^{1,3}. Later development led to further increase in boiler capacity to 3000 t_{DS}/day and in steam parameters attacking 10 MPa and 500 °C. Fired black liquor dry solids content also risen to 85 % wt.^{2,4} by high dry solids (HDS) concentrator introduction. Air and boiler feedwater regenerative heating has been introduced as well. Latest development led to installation of regeneration boiler with double capacity, steam parameters above 10 MPa and 510 °C and extensive air and boiler feedwater regenerative heating and with flue gas coolers⁵. Such steam parameters already approach those employed in common subcritical fossil fuels fired thermal power plants. All these features enabled the current paper mills equipped with such high power boilers to approach electric energy self sufficiency and reduce the amount of fossil fuels used for additional steam generation. One of the regeneration boilers vendors – Valmet – states that with current high efficiency boilers more than 4.3 ton of steam can be produced per one ton of combusted dry solids in the boiler⁶. Similar experiences are reported from operation of a 6000 t_{DS}/day boiler in China⁵. In order to be competitive on the market, firing black liquor with at least 70 % dry solids, using no more than 8 % of produced steam for sootblowing, reducing oxygen content in flue gases to 2 % vol. and reducing final flue gas temperature to stack below 200 °C is recommended. Future development aims at firing black liquor with above 90 % wt. dry solids, still increasing boiler capacity and steam pressures and reduced NO_x levels in flue gas⁴. Andritz company reports on its webpage on HERB design (highly efficient regeneration boiler) that can be scaled up to 12000 t_{DS}/day⁷. Even comparably “small” boilers are currently equipped with several above mentioned features as can be seen in the case of paper mill in Ružomberok, Slovak republic as reported by Andritz⁸. As is obvious from the state of the art of the recovery boilers development, it leads to increased own steam consumption at low, middle and even high pressure level in the steam production process, thereby boosting the live steam production and consequently the steam turbine power output. Amount of steam condensates

available at high temperatures thus increased significantly. Utilization of flue gas cooler and HDS concentrator provides additional heat available at 80 to 150 °C that can be used in the air and boiler feedwater preheating. Summed up, far more heat stemming from boiler and auxiliaries operation is available than with boilers missing the high efficiency features. This heat competes in turn with heat available in the paper mill in the temperature range 50 to 100 (120) °C that can be used either within the paper mill or in delivering hot chemically treated water and steam condensates from paper mill to regeneration boiler. Thus to be able to efficiently exploit all modern recovery boilers features that raise power production from black liquor, it is crucial that the paper mill integrates the modern boiler with existing utilities system respecting its particular features given by its historical on site evolution— this leads to site-particular integration solutions that cannot be fully standardized.

Due to valid Slovak legislation, producers of electric energy that in turn is consumed in the producers local electricity distribution system, ergo does physically not leave the locality where it has been produced, have to pay certain fees which in the end lowers the price of the internally produced electric energy. According to the Decree of the Regulatory Office for Network Industries No. 18/2017 Z.z., such electricity producers have to pay the tariff for system services (TSS) and the tariff for system operation (TPS) (both in €/MWh of produced electricity) and a fix monthly fee for access into national electricity distribution system in €/kW of installed electric output⁹. Tariffs and fees valid for the year 2018 according to Decision of the Regulatory Office for Network Industries No. 0003/2018/E and No.0009/2018/E are as follows: TSS 6.8919 €/MWh; TPS 26.2011 €/MWh and the access fee on very high voltage level (52 to 110 kV) is 30 % of 2836.5 €/MW/month = 850.95 €/MW/month^{10,11}. The only fee such electric energy producer is not eligible to pay is the tariff for electric energy distribution incl. the tariff for electric energy losses that together yields 7.4488 €/MWh¹¹. The price of electric energy as commodity that can be bought on market for the year 2019 (2019 baseload futures) varied in central Europe during 2017 between 26 and 38 €/MWh¹². The final price (value) of to be internally produced and consumed electric energy in the year 2019 is thus in the range 34 to 46 €/MWh. This is significantly lower than the expected industrial end user electricity price that can be estimated in the range 75 to 95 €/MWh (baseload, without including full fix fee of 2836.5 €/MW/month for access into national electricity distribution system on the very high voltage level) which is an important fact somewhat discouraging the industry from internal electric energy production and might thus negatively impact the benefit of high power regeneration boiler installation as well.

The aim of our case study is to analyze how well this modern, by design very efficient cogeneration system integrated into existing particular paper mill energy balance with respect to:

- the extent of BAT features exploitation during real boiler operation
- the existing conflict in waste heat sources utilization
- the true benefit of condensing power production with regards to aforementioned Slovak legislation
- the potential for the improvement of present state

Case study

The object of our study is a part of central steam and power plant (CSPP) located in a paper mill in Slovakia. This part contain a modern 1750 t_{DS}/day regeneration boiler with nominal steam production capacity of 315 t/h equipped with best available technology features, a 60 MW_e condensing steam turbine equipped with three steam extractions and auxiliary devices⁸. Its scheme is provided in Figure 1. The BAT features of the regeneration boiler include:

- a black liquor concentrator (HD concentrator) raising the dry solids content in the black liquor from 70 to 85 %wt. as received from the evaporator plant up to 85 % wt., thereby increasing the black liquor heating value⁸
- a partial condenser serving for water preheat before deaeration that is supplied with vapours from the black liquor concentrator
- a combustion air preheating train that stepwise uses the low, middle and high pressure steam extracted from the steam turbine to increase the combustion air temperature up to 210 °C
- a boiler feedwater regenerative heating train raising the water temperature up to 215 °C
- a flue gas cooler lowering the boiler stack losses and utilizing the recuperated heat to preheat water before deaeration
- very high design steam parameters reaching nearly 10 MPa and 500 °C⁸ but somewhat lowered in real operation

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of the system under study. BL = black liquor; CW = cooling water; DEA = deaerator; ECO = economizer; FGC = flue gas cooler

Figure 2. Schematic depiction of the existing condensates management and boiler feedwater preparation and preheating train. CCT = condensates collection tank; CHTW = chemically treated water; A, B, C = potential of system performance improvement

The steam turbine is equipped with water cooled steam condenser supplied by circulation cooling water that allows for steam expansion up to 5 kPa (a) thereby increasing power production. All those features lead to significant steam production increase as well as internal steam consumption increase compared to older boilers

per ton of fired black liquor. Secondly power production is maximized while maintaining the needed steam export to the paper mill. The condensing part of the steam turbine has sufficient capacity to cope with its variable seasonal steam demand. Steam is extracted from the turbine at high pressure (HP, 1.7 to 2.3 MPa), middle pressure (MP, around 1.1 MPa (g)) and low pressure (LP, around 0.5 MPa (g)) level.

Steam condensates management and fresh chemically treated water preheat system is depicted in Figure 2. It must be noted that condensates return to boiler feedwater preparation train at high temperatures, often above 100 °C. This limits the exploitation of waste heat sources from paper mill (denoted as A and C in the Figure 2) that already are partly integrated in this system. Further limitation is represented by the new regeneration boiler – denoted as B in the figure – as it has plenty of its own low potential heat that is used in further boiler feedwater preheat (see Figure 1).

Boiler operation during 2016 and 2017, e.g. during the analyzed time period exhibited following features:

- deaerator works at 150 to 153 °C that is by 5 to 8 °C lower temperature than achievable with given LP steam pressure. Increase of deaeration temperature to 158 °C has been achieved during field test. Deaeration at full steam pressure that complies with the field test conditions is recommended by literature².
- steam consumption in the deaerator is around 8 to 14 t/h depending on solids fired in the boiler, water entering the deaerator has around 20 °C lower temperature than the deaeration temperature which in turn limits the heat output of the water preheater utilizing heat from flue gas cooler
- flue gas to stack exist at 10 to 20 °C higher than the minimum achievable temperature with full flue gas cooler operation and represents approximately 1.5 to 3 MW heat lost to stack
- oxygen level in flue gas is around 3 % vol. which is higher than 2 % vol. recommended²
- dry solids in combusted black liquor vary between 80 and 85 %wt. which is somewhat lower than the maximum achieved value of 86 %wt. Firing BL with lower dry solids content has been recommended by external experts to reduce the observed beginning corrosion in boiler.
- both feedwater and combustion air are preheated to maximum temperature achievable with given HP steam pressure which complies with BAT
- steam parameters exiting the boiler have been lowered due to boiler availability issues connected with observed beginning corrosion in boiler to 8.7 MPa / 475 °C that represents a quite significant negative deviation from design values. Further 0.4 to 0.6 MPa and around 5 °C are lost due to the friction and heat losses from live steam pipeline before steam enters the steam turbine. Colder than designed steam entering the turbine coupled with very deep vacuum achieved in the turbine condenser is likely to yield wetter than designed steam at the turbine exhaust which might lead to turbine damage in long term.

Results and discussion

Due to limited scope of this contribution, we focus just on two issues: increase in waste heat utilization in the boiler feedwater preparation and assessment of the value of electric energy produced.

Field test showed the possibility of temperature increase in the deaerator by at least 5 °C which in turn allows warmer water to enter it. However as resulted from analyses there is just very limited space for warmer inlet water production for the deaerator: the water preheater works nearly at full capacity which still is much lower than heat flux obtainable from the flue gas cooler. No other heat exchanger is available for consumption of heat from flue gas cooler. On the other hand condensates from boiler internal steam consumption that mix with inlet water have roughly the same temperature as is in the deaerator (see Figure 1) and a decrease in their temperature would thus be welcome. Combining higher temperature in the deaerator with lower temperature of boiler condensates creates enough space for full flue gas cooler potential utilization. This requires replacement of water preheater or installing additional one and requires creation of heat sink for boiler condensates heat content away from boiler feedwater preparation train. We proposed installation of another flash tank for boiler steam condensates next to the existing one that would operate at around 80 kPa (g). Condensates from existing tank would be flashed in the new one, creating a very low pressure flash steam that would be utilized in cold combustion air preheat before the LP steam preheat. Condensates from the new flash tank would be then pumped to the deaerator at around 115 °C instead of the current nearly 160 °C. For the full boiler load case when 300 t/h of boiler feedwater have to be produced this creates an opportunity to utilize 3.7 MW extra from flue gas cooler that results partly in lower LP steam consumption for air preheat and partly in lower MP steam consumption for boiler feedwater preheat prior to ECO1 (see Figure 1). Thereby the flue gas cooler could be continuously operated at full load capacity, as documented also in Figure 3. The still missing heat in the water preheat train could be supplied in the condensates system (see Figure 2, location A) if an investment in water splitting is considered to maintain the maximum water temperature of 80 °C (see Figure 2, location B).

Figure 3. Heat flux data obtained from boiler feedwater preparation system heat balancing procedure. A – Heat flux still available in the flue gas currently not utilized, B – Additional heat flux needed for water preheat before deaeration by deaeration temperature increase, C – Cumulative additional heat flux needed for water preheat before deaeration by deaeration temperature increase and boiler condensates flash.

Financial benefit from saving 10 to 17 GJ/h (see Figure 3 line C) low pressure steam would be realised either by marginal fuel saving (natural gas) lessened by a small decrease in backpressure power production or by increased condensing power production at unchanged marginal fuel consumption (less feasible option). Net heat efficiency of steam production in the studied regeneration boiler system would be thereby increased by up to 2 %. Using the natural gas and electricity prices discussed below the expected saving if considering the fuel saving option is in the range 45 to 80 €/h, yielding approximately 350 to 650 ths. € per year.

When dealing with electric energy production, one has to realise that even backpressure electricity production on a steam turbine is associated with certain costs. Even if neglecting auxiliary electricity consumption, due to the fact that 1 MWh electric energy is produced from appr. 1.05 MWh heat energy in a backpressure steam turbine (mechanic and electric efficiency), 3.8 GJ energy from steam is needed to produce 1 MWh electric energy. In the particular case under study, marginal heat source for steam production are two somewhat obsolete steam boilers fired with natural gas working with thermal efficiency of around 90 %. Thus, if an 2016 - 2017 average large consumer natural gas price of 5 \$/MMBTU is considered, this yields steam cost of appr. 5 €/GJ including some margin for gas trader and gas distribution company. In the end we see that the 2016 - 2017 cost of backpressure electricity production is around 19 €/MWh. As stated in the Introduction part, the value of internally produced electric energy in Slovak republic is in the range 34 to 46 €/MWh, leaving a somewhat meagre net benefit from own power production of appr. 20 €/MWh. With current (January 2018) natural gas costs exceeding 7.5 \$/MMBTU¹³ the net benefit would further shrink to 10 to 15 €/MWh.

Condensing power production requires larger amount of heat in steam than backpressure one, since the turbine exhaust cannot be used effectively due to its temperature around 35 to 40 °C and has therefore to be wasted in cooling water. Marginal power production cost in condensing steam turbine is at least 11 GJ per MWh for high quality live steam entering the turbine. This with respect to above marginal steam price yields 2016 - 2017 condensing power production cost of at least 55 €/MWh and can be near to 60 €/MWh when considering auxiliary power production (cooling water pumps, cooling tower fans etc.). Since it exceeds the in house power production value by at least 10 €/MWh, it is infeasible as long as there is any natural gas that could be saved by lowering steam consumption for condensing power production. On the other hand, for some other paper mill firing just black liquor and wood residues for steam production, steam is cheap and even condensing power production could make sense if steam surplus exists (summer conditions).

Conclusions

Modern and efficient regeneration boilers coupled with highly efficient steam turbines are the key for self sufficiency of paper mills regarding their heat and electricity needs. Our study stresses the fact that those energetic devices have to be incorporated into existing electricity and heat management systems of individual paper mills that are likely to have adopted unique features through decades of past development influenced by

local conditions and legislation. Therefore attention has to be paid in respecting those features when commissioning and operating new energetic devices, lest a part of their superior design efficiency does not translate into operational efficiency. Our case study incorporating a modern recovery boiler and existing system of boiler feedwater preparation and preheating has shown that a part of the available heat from regeneration boiler cannot be used in the process unless some operational parameters are changed and some investment is made, not foreseen in the design stage. Proposed system changes have potential to increase the boiler and boiler feedwater preparation system thermal efficiency by up to 2 % and to translate into financial savings in the order of 350 to 650 ths. € per year. As a second important message we elucidate the value of in-house produced electricity that due to valid legislation is just moderately positive in the backpressure electricity case but is strongly negative for electricity produced in condensing steam turbines. From our point of view is the effort undertaken by boiler and turbines designers to reach still higher steam parameters produced in regeneration boilers in order to maximize electricity production from black liquor questionable.

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